

NDAC/LO/105
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22nd NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

The Step 2/3 (or sphere reconstitution and determination of astrometric parameters) will consist of five major program modules: *SORT23*, which takes data from tapes generated by the Set Solution, order them according to the object identification number and put them back on tapes; *LOAD23*, which read the ordered data back on disc and prepares other files needed for subsequent modules; *ACCU23*, which accumulates the normal equations for the RGC zero points while updating the astrometric parameters; *SOLV23*, which solve the RGC zero points and global parameters; and finally *OUTP23*, which produces tape files with the astrometric results, RGC zero points, etc.

All modules except the last one (*OUTP23*) have been written and are currently subject to large-scale tests involving observations of all the 114,488 stars in IC1 for periods of 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 years. (These data were simulated by means of a special program, *SIP23* [Ver. 2, November 1987], which will be fully described in a forthcoming report.) The results so far are very encouraging for the final accuracy as well as in regard of data management and software reliability. These tests will probably go on until March/April 1988.

Documentation of the Step 2/3 programs proceeds in parallel with these tests. A single *Reference and User's Manual* is foreseen, with the following chapters: Introduction, Mathematical description, Functional overview, Functional description of main programs, User's Manual.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

Some algorithmic improvements have been introduced (103) and further experiments made concerning the IFOV pointing strategy for binaries with separation $< 10''$ (104), the latter resulting in a proposal presented and accepted at the November HST meeting (C).

Working papers:

- C = NDAC/LO/101 (Lindegren, 1987 Oct 5):
A posteriori variances for least-squares estimates with weight reduction
- C = NDAC/LO/102 (Lindegren, 1987 Oct 6):
A crude Earth ephemeris for TYCHO astrometry
- C = NDAC/LO/103 (Söderhjelm, 1987 Oct 13):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Vc
- C = NDAC/LO/104 (Söderhjelm, 1987 Nov 11):
Some tests of the binary pointing strategy
- C (Söderhjelm and Lindegren, 1987 Nov 12):
Double star and veiling glare processing for the Input Catalogue
- C (Lindegren, 1987 Nov 13):
Proposal for a point comparison of apparent positions etc